

Comparative Effects of Isometric Quadriceps Training, Glucosamine and Chondroitin Sulphate Iontophoresis on Pain Intensity and Physical Functions of Patients with Knee Osteoarthritis

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Abstract

This study was with a view to comparing the effective means of alleviating pain and improving physical functions in patients with knee osteoarthritis using quadriceps strengthening exercises, glucosamine and chondroitin

sulphate iontophoresis. Seventy-eight participants with grade II knee OA were purposively selected and randomly assigned to three groups using fish bowl technique. Group one participants received 1g of glucosamine sulphate (GS) through iontophoresis while group two received 1g of chondroitin sulphate (CS) iontophoresis (40mA- min as dosage) using trans-arthral electrode placement technique twice a week, for 12 weeks. Group three participants had intervention in the form of quadriceps muscle strengthening exercise (1RM, 10 reps and 3 sets), which was a baseline treatment for all the groups. Pain intensity, active knee range of motion and physical function were assessed. Descriptive statistics, ANOVA and Kruskal-wallis test were used to analyze the data. Alpha level was set at $p \leq 0.05$. The three modes of interventions significantly alleviated pain ($p = 0.001$), improved the Functional Activity Level and active ranges of motion ($p = 0.001$) in the groups after 12 weeks. Although, the administration of Quadriceps strengthening exercise alone, significantly improved the Functional Activity Level than Chondroitin sulphate iontophoresis and Glucosamine sulphate ($H = 19.89$, $p = 0.001$). However; there was no significant difference in the active range of motion across the 3 groups. In conclusion, Quadriceps strengthening exercise, Glucosamine and Chondroitin sulphate iontophoresis were effective in alleviating pain, enhancing range of motions and improving physical functions. However, Quadriceps strengthening exercise showed higher efficacy compared to others.

Introduction

Osteoarthritis (OA) is a common degenerative disorder of the articular cartilage associated with hypertrophic bone changes and it is also referred to as a clinical syndrome accompanied by varying degrees of functional limitation and reduced quality of life [1-3]. Zhang and Jordan described osteoarthritis as a chronic disease characterized by subchondral bone sclerosis which leads to the formation of bone cysts and marginal osteophytes [4]. It is characterized by pain that is worse with activity and associated with only a short period of early morning stiffness; unlike rheumatoid arthritis (RA) that is commonly associated with early morning stiffness that lasts more than one hour [5]. Osteoarthritis is a leading musculoskeletal disorder that reduces quality of life of patients, with pain and loss of function being the most prominent symptom [6-7].

The main goal of managing OA includes alleviation of pain and improving functional abilities and the main drugs of choice are usually Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) although, not without potential hazards if administered by oral and through injections. The adverse effects include gastrointestinal disorders and reduction in body immunity, particularly in the elderly [8]. In recent time, non-pharmacological strategies are the first line of management as recommended by most clinical guidelines for knee OA [9-11]. Non-pharmacologic approach, especially physiotherapy, often starts with lower extremity strengthening exercises for 20-30 minutes per day, gait training, education, behavioral intervention and weight loss, in order to effectively alleviate pain and reduce disability [12].

Amongst drugs which have been speculated to be disease-modifying are glucosamine and chondroitin, but the magnitude of their effects remains unclear and controversial [13]. Most clinical researches suggested that glucosamine and chondroitin show efficacy in slowing progression of the disease, or regenerate damaged

cartilage [14]. Most of these clinical trials adopted either the use of oral or intramuscular injections in the administration of glucosamine and chondroitin sulfate whereas there are alternative methods involving the use of electromotive forces in medical rehabilitation field [8, 14]. Glucosamine is being considered to be completely safe, as it is a natural, non-toxic compound that alleviates joint pains and retards loss of cartilage [15, 16, 17, 18, 19]. Similarly, several clinical trials have also shown that chondroitin sulphate slows down the narrowing of joint space as shown on plain radiograph of knee OA. It is believed to stop the degradation of cartilage, and equally, restoring the loss. Chondroitin sulphate is a sulfur-containing amino acids which are essential building blocks for cartilage molecules in the human body [20, 21, 22, 23].

Exercise therapy is an age-long therapy and is regarded as the cornerstone of conservative management for knee OA [24]. The application of adjunct therapy using transdermal Electromotive Drug Administration (EMDA) is gaining acceptance in clinical physiotherapy practice [25]. However, it is unknown if the combination of quadriceps exercise with iontophoretic application of glucosamine and chondroitin sulphate cream will be more effective in the management of knee osteoarthritis than exercise alone. It was hypothesized that there would be no significant differences in the effects of iontophoretic applications of glucosamine sulphate, chondroitin sulphate and quadriceps strengthening exercise alone on pain intensity, disability and active range of motion among patients with knee OA.

Methodology

Participants

Participants for this study were individuals with knee OA receiving treatment at the Physiotherapy Departments of Osun State University Teaching Hospital, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Included in this study were patients aged 30 years and older with history of knee OA not less than three months, radiological evidence of knee OA and grade II Knee OA on Kellgren classification. Excluded were patients with history of knee surgery, neuromuscular and musculoskeletal diseases such as rheumatoid arthritis, poliomyelitis, muscular dystrophy, septic arthritis. Also excluded are those with cardiac disorder(s) who were using cardiac pacemaker and those who have been on any intra articular steroid therapy and other forms of intra articular therapy within two (2) months before the commencement of this study.

Research Design and Sampling Techniques

The study was a Randomized Controlled Trial. The sample size for this study was determined using a sample size formula of Wayne [26]. Eighty-seven patients who met inclusion criteria were randomly assigned to three (3) groups. However, 78 participants completed the study (Figure1). Purposive sampling technique was used to recruit 26 participants for each group, but to give room for attrition, 29 participants were recruited for each group. and they were randomly assigned using fish bowl technique.

Instruments

The major test instruments were Electrical Muscle stimulator (Model: Endomed 582, India), Visual Analogues Scale (VAS), Plastic Goniometer was used to measure the knee range of motion (Model E-Z Read™) and Western Ontario and McMaster University – WOMAC Osteoarthritis index Questionnaire was used to assess the physical function while reagents such as Glucosamine sulphate cream (glucosamine 8% w/w), (Urah) and Chondroitin sulphate cream (Vitabiotics) were applied topically.

Study Site

The study site was the treatment cubicles of Physiotherapy Department, Osun State University Teaching Hospital, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria.

Procedures

Ethical approval was obtained from the Health Research and Ethics Committee of Osun State University Teaching Hospital, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria. Informed consent was also obtained from the individual participants. The participants in group 1 received 1g (2 Finger-Tip Unit, [FTU]) of glucosamine sulphate iontophoresis, those in group 2 had 1g of Chondroitin Sulphate through iontophoresis while participants in Group 3 had quadriceps muscle strengthening through resisted exercise using 1RM, 10 repetitions and 3 sets which served as baseline treatment for all the groups. The Repetition Maximum (RM) was determined for the affected limb by measuring the heaviest weight the patient could carry for a maximum of 10 repetitions [27]. This was

determined for all the patients at baseline, 4th and 8th week. The value of RM determined the amount of weight used to strengthen the quadriceps of the affected limb for each patient throughout the exercise phase. The patients maintained sitting position on a quadriceps bench with knee flexed to 90° while strap was also used to stabilize and maintain the hip joints. An ankle strap was used to fasten the required weight for isometric strengthen at the lower one-third of the affected limb. They were instructed to slowly extend the knee, maintaining the quadriceps isometric contraction for 3 to 5 seconds; and then slowly returned to the starting position. Each patient flexed and extended the knee joint performing 3 sets of 10 repetitions each. A brief rest period of 3 seconds was allowed in between each set and they were treated twice a week for 12 weeks. There was standardization of procedures for all participants. Prior to exercise, each patient used 25% of determined RM (10 repetition) to warm the tissues (warm-up phase) in order to improve vascularization of the area and they were instructed not to hold breaths throughout the isometric phase of the exercise and also avoid sporting activities throughout the period of study [28].

Quadruple Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) was used to rate the pain experienced by each patient. The cut off points on the pain VAS was marked as: no pain (0–4 mm), mild pain (5–44 mm), moderate pain (45–74 mm), and severe pain (75–100 mm), [29]. The pain rating scale was explained to each patient. The VAS was found to be effective in assessing osteoarthritis knee pain [30]. Pain intensity was rated during active knee flexion. Test–retest reliability has been shown to be good, but higher among literate ($r = 0.94$, $P = 0.001$) than illiterate patients ($r = 0.71$, $P = 0.001$), [31].

The active knee flexion was measured in prone lying position using standard procedure [13]. Plastic goniometer was placed on the lateral aspect of the knee joint with the fixed proximal reference pointing towards the head of the greater trochanter, fulcrum was at the distal lateral condyle of the femur while the moveable arm was at the line pointing towards the lateral malleolus. The knee joint of the patients were actively bent and range of motion obtained was recorded.

Physical function was assessed using the Western Ontario McMaster Osteoarthritis Questionnaire (WOMAC). It consists three sub-scales including pain assessment, available active range of motion and physical function. WOMAC Osteoarthritis index questionnaire is one of the various outcome measures that has been designed and validated for monitoring a number of clinical conditions including osteoarthritis [32]. The physical function sub-scale was used to assess the physical function of patients with knee OA in this study. There are 17 items on the physical function sub-

scale, it rated on 5 point Likert scale ranging from 0 to 4 whereby “0 = none and “4 = extreme”. The minimum obtainable score is “0” indicating best physical function while the maximum obtainable is “68” indicating poor physical function. Obtained score for physical function

was divided by total possible score and multiplied by 100 and reported in percentage. The Yoruba version of WOMAC questionnaire with reliability coefficient of 0.83 was utilized for the study for those who were not literate enough to understand the English version[28].

Figure 1: CONSORT for Recruiting and Research Procedures

Procedure for the Administration of Glucosamine Sulphate Iontophoresis

To deliver GS gels through the skin, an electrical stimulator machine (Model: Endomed 582, India) was used with the aid of electrodes. One (1) gram of glucosamine sulphate (2FTU) cream was placed on positive electrode lint (being positively charged), [33, 34] for GS Iontophoresis Group 1 participants. The Galvanic current mode in the Electrical Stimulator (Endomed 582) was used. The dose applied was 40mA-min (2mA x 20minutes) for each subject in GS Iontophoresis [35, 13]. The active (positive) electrode was placed on the side where the participants experienced higher pain intensity, either at the medial or lateral side of the knee joint (using valgus and varus stress tests).

Trans-arthral electrode placement technique (Plate) was used for the procedure of iontophoresis. The skin areas where electrodes were fastened were cleansed with methylated spirit (70% alcohol) to minimize the risk of burns and increase sensitivity [36]. Both electrodes were held in place by an adhesive strap. Each participant had intervention(s) twice a week for 12 weeks. The electrode Lints were soaked in 3ml of tap water.

Procedure for the Administration of Chondroitin Sulphate Iontophoresis

One (1) gram of CS (2FTU) cream was placed on positive electrode (being positively charged), [33, 34] for CS

Iontophoresis. Other procedures adopted were as for participants in the GS group.

Figure 2: Transarthral Electrode Placement

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics of frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation were used to summarize the

data obtained. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to compare pain intensity, knee range of motion and physical characteristics across the groups. Repeated measured Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to compare within and across groups at baseline and 4th, 8th and 12 weeks. Post Hoc Analysis (Least Significant Difference (LSD) was used to determine trend of differences in the groups. kruskal-wallis test was used to compare physical functions across the three groups. The data were analysed using the Statistical Package of Social Science (SPSS) version 22. Alpha level was set at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results

Distribution of Gender, Affectation site, Age and duration of onset of OA

The result showed that there are 11 (42.3%) male and 15 (57.7%) female among participants who received

glucosamine sulphate iontophoresis. Eleven (42.3%) of the participants in the GS group have right knee OA while 15 (57.7%) have left knee OA. In the Chondroitin Sulphate (CS) group, 10 participants (38.5%) are male and fourteen (53.8%) were having right knee OA. Nine participants (34.6%) out of 26 in the control group have right knee OA and 11 (42.3%) are male. The mean age of participants in GS group was 59.58 ± 12.42 years while that of CS and control groups are also presented in Table 1. The mean duration of onset of participants in GS group was 4.69 ± 1.41 months while that of CS and control groups were 4.77 ± 1.22 months and 4.42 ± 1.35 months respectively. The result of analysis of variance (ANOVA) showed that there were no significant differences in the duration of onset, weight and height across the 3 groups. The Post hoc Analysis is presented in Table 2.

Table 1: Across- Group Comparison of Physical Characteristics (N=26 for each group)

	Glucosamine sulphate		Chondroitin sulphate		Quadriceps Exercise		F-ratio	p-value
	Mean	±SD	Mean	±SD	Mean	±SD		
Age (Years)	59.58	12.42	55.96	9.15	63.65	11.17	3.04	0.005
Weight (Kg)	70.35	7.54	75.50	11.21	76.31	9.71	2.61	0.008
Height (m)	1.59	0.09	1.57	0.95	7.29	29.11	1.04	0.361
BMI (kg/m ²)	28.09	3.12	30.64	4.78	30.64	4.22	3.33	0.042

Note: *Significant at $p < 0.05$

Table 2: Across-Groups Mean Changes in Physical Characteristics (Post hoc Analysis)

	i	J	Mean Changes (i-j)	p-value
Age	2	3	-7.72	0.002*
BMI	1	2	-2.54	0.003*
		3	-2.59	0.003*
	3	1	2.59	0.031*

Note: *Significant at $p < 0.05$; 1; GS, 2; CS and 3; CONTROL

Comparison of Pain Intensities and Ranges of Motion within-Glucosamine Sulphate Iontophoresis Group

The mean of pain intensity was 66.54 ± 8.92 on a 100mm-point Quadruple Visual Analogue Rating Scale (VAS) for participants in GS group (glucosamine sulphate iontophoresis) at baseline, while the mean pain intensity at 4th, 8th and 12th week are presented in the Table 3. The result of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) showed that was significant difference in pain intensity within the GS group participants ($F = 279.44, p = 0.001$). The Post Hoc analysis (LSD) showed that the pain intensity on passive knee flexion at 4th weeks of GS group participants was significantly lower than that of baseline ($p = 0.001$) and also the pain intensity on passive knee flexion on at 8th week of GS group participants was significantly lower than that of baseline ($p = 0.001$). Similarly, the pain intensity on passive knee flexion at 12th week of GS group

participants was significantly lower than that of baseline ($p = 0.001$).

The mean of range of motion was 96.39 ± 8.86 at baseline of participants in GS group while the mean of range of motion were $105.42 \pm 7.64, 110.89 \pm 6.87$ and 119.23 ± 5.44 after 4th, 8th and 12th week respectively. The ANOVA showed that there was significant difference in range of motion within GS group participants ($F = 131.82, p = 0.001$), (Table 3 - Appendix). The Post Hoc analysis (LSD) showed that the range of motion at 4th week within GS group participants was significantly higher than that of baseline ($p = 0.001$) and also the range of motion at 8th week within GS group participants was significantly higher than that of baseline ($p = 0.001$). Similarly, the range of motion at 12th week within GS group participants was significantly higher than that of baseline ($p = 0.001$) as shown in Table 4.

Comparison of Pain Intensities and Ranges of Motions of Participants within-Chondroitin Sulphate Iontophoresis Group

The mean of pain intensity was 71.54 ±6.75 on a 100mm-point Quadruple Visual Analogue Rating Scale (VAS) for participants in CS group (chondroitin sulphate iontophoresis) at baseline, while the mean pain intensity at 4th, 8th and 12th week are presented in the Table 3. The ANOVA showed that was significant difference in pain intensity within the CS group participants (F = 530.08, p = 0.001). The post hoc analysis (LSD) showed that the pain intensity on passive knee flexion at 4th week of CS group participants was significantly lower than that of baseline (p= 0.001) and also the pain intensity on passive knee flexion at 8th week of CS group participants was significantly lower than that of baseline (p = 0.001). Similarly, the pain intensity on passive knee flexion on a 100mm-point Quadruple Visual Analogue Rating Scale (VAS) at 12th week of CS group participants was significantly lower than that of baseline (p = 0.001).

The mean of range of motion was 92.39 ±10.28 at baseline of participants in CS group while the mean of range of motion were 104.54 ±8.77, 115.69 ±7.30 and 124.42 ±5.64 after 4th, 8th and 12th week respectively. The ANOVA showed that there was significant difference in range of motion within CS group participants (F= 74.88, p= 0.001) (Table 3). The Post Hoc analysis (LSD) showed that the range of motion at 4th week within CS group participants was significantly higher than that of baseline (p= 0.001) and also the range of motion at 8th week within CS group participants was significantly higher than that of baseline (p = 0.001). Similarly, the range of motion at 12th week within CS group participants was significantly higher than that of baseline (p = 0.001) as shown in Table 5.

Comparison of Pain Intensities and Ranges of Motions within-Isometric Exercise Group

The mean of pain intensity was 66.40±8.10 on a 100mm-point Quadruple Visual Analogue Rating Scale (VAS) for participants in Exercise group at baseline, while the mean pain intensity at 4th, 8th and 12th week are presented in the Table 3. The ANOVA showed that there was significant difference in pain intensity within the control group participants (F = 441.68, p = 0.001). The Post Hoc analysis (LSD) showed that the pain intensity on passive knee flexion on VAS at 4th week of control group participants was significantly lower than that of baseline (p= 0.001) and also the pain intensity on passive knee flexion at 8th weeks of control group participants was significantly lower than that of baseline (p = 0.001). Similarly, the pain intensity on VAS at 12th week of control group participants was significantly lower than that of baseline (p = 0.001).

The mean of range of motion was 97.76 ±6.06 at baseline of participants in control group while the mean of range of motion were 107.46 ±8.98, 116.92 ±5.20 and 120.48 ±22.82 after 4th, 8th and 12th week respectively. The ANOVA showed that there was significant difference in range of motion within control group participants (F= 44.61, p= 0.001), (Table 3). The Post Hoc analysis (LSD) showed that the range of motion at 4th week within control group participants was significantly higher than that of baseline (p= 0.001) and also the range of motion at 8th weeks within control group participants was significantly higher than that of baseline (p = 0.001). Similarly, the range of motion at 12th week within control group participants was significantly higher than that of baseline (p = 0.001) as shown in Table 6.

Table 4: Mean Changes of Pain Intensities and Ranges of Motion within-Glucosamine Sulphate Iontophoresis Group Participants

Variables	I	J	Mean Changes (i-j)	p-value
Pain Intensity	Baseline	4 th week	1.77	0.001
		8 th week	2.58	0.001
		12 th week	3.58	0.001
Range of Motion	Baseline	4 th week	22.85	0.001
		8 th week	19.81	0.001
		12 th week	22.85	0.001

Note: Significant at p < 0.05

Table 5: Mean Changes of Range of motion of participants within-Chondroitin Sulphate Iontophoresis Group

Variables	I	J	Mean Changes (i-j)	P
Pain Intensity	Baseline	4 th week	2.00	0.01
		8 th week	3.77	0.01
		12 th week	5.58	0.01
Range of Motion	Baseline	4 th week	32.04	0.01

		8 th week	19.89	0.01
		12 th week	32.04	0.01

Note: Significant at p < 0.05

Table 6: Within-Exercise Group Mean Changes of Pain Intensities and Ranges of Motion of Participants

Variables	I	J	Mean Changes (i-j)	p-value
Pain Intensity	Baseline	4 th week	1.95	0.001
		8 th week	3.52	0.001
		12 th week	4.96	0.001
Range of Motion	Baseline	4 th week	9.70	0.001
		8 th week	19.16	0.001
		12 th week	-22.72	0.001

Note: Significant at p < 0.05

Across-Groups Comparison of Pain Intensities and Ranges of Motions of Participants

The means of pain intensity were 66.54 ±8.92, 71.54 ±6.75 and 66.40 ±8.10 on a 10-point Quadruple Visual Analogue Rating Scale (VAS) for participants in GS, CS and control group respectively at baseline while the means of pain intensities at 4th, 8th and 12th week across the groups were presented in Table 7. The means of range of motion were 96.38 ±8.86, 92.39 ±10.28 and 97.76 ±6.06 for participants in GS, CS and control group respectively at baseline while the means of range of motion at 4th, 8th and 12th week across the 3 groups were presented in Table 7

The ANOVA showed that there were no significant differences in pain intensity at baseline (F = 3.48, p = 0.004), 4th week (F=1.34, p=0.002). However, there were significant differences in pain intensity at 8th week (F = 16.41, p = 0.001) and 12th week (F = 44.21, p = 0.001) respectively. The result of the post hoc analysis (LSD) showed that the pain intensity of control group participants was significantly reduced than that of GS and CS groups (p= 0.002) while that of CS group was significantly reduced than that of GSO4 group (0.002) as shown in table 8. However, the ANOVA showed that there were no significant differences in range of motion across the groups at baseline, 4th, 8th and 12th week respectively across the groups.

Table 7: Across-Groups Comparison of Pain Intensity and Range of Motion of Participants (N=26)

Variable		Glucosamine Sulphate		Chondroitin Sulphate		Control		F-ratio	p- value
		Mean	±SD	Mean	±SD	Mean	±SD		
PI	Baseline	66.54	8.92	71.54	6.75	66.40	8.10	0.00	0.951
	4 th week	48.85	8.64	51.92	10.21	45.77	9.87	1.34	0.251
	8 th week	40.77	6.28	33.85	9.83	31.20	8.81	16.41	0.001
	12 th week	30.77	6.88	15.77	9.02	16.80	6.27	44.21	0.001
ROM	Baseline	96.39	8.86	92.39	10.28	97.76	6.06	0.33	0.570
	4 th week	105.42	7.64	104.89	8.77	108.42	6.30	2.01	0.161
	8 th week	110.89	6.87	115.69	7.30	116.92	5.20	10.87	0.215
	12 th week	119.23	5.44	124.42	5.64	120.48	22.82	0.11	0.747

Note: PI=Pain intensity, ROM= Range of motion

Table 8: Across-Groups Mean Changes of Pain Intensities of Participants at baseline, 4th week, 8th week and 12th week

	Variables	I	J	Mean Changes (i-j)	p-value
8 th week	Pain Intensity	1	2	0.69	0.001
		1	3	0.96	0.001
12 th week	Pain Intensity	1	2	1.50	0.001
		1	3	1.40	0.001

Note: 1= Glucosamine sulphate group, 2=Chondroitin sulphate group, 3=Control group.

Within-Groups Comparison of Physical Functions of Participants

The mean of physical function was 62.53 ±7.21 on a WOMAC scale for participants in GS group (glucosamine sulphate iontophoresis) at baseline, while the mean of physical function at 4th, 8th and 12th week are presented in Table 9. The result of Kruskal-wallis shows that there were significant differences in physical function within the GS group participants (H = 205.63, p = 0.001). The mean of physical function was 57.43 ±5.84 on a WOMAC scale for participants in CS group (chondroitin sulphate iontophoresis) at baseline, while the mean of physical function at 4th, 8th and 12th week are presented in Table 9. The result of Kruskal-wallis shows that there were significant differences in physical function within the CS group participants (H = 423.37, p = 0.001). The mean of physical function was 52.94 ±3.97 on a WOMAC scale for participants in control group at baseline, while the mean of physical function at 4th, 8th and 12th week are presented in Table 9. The result of Kruskal-wallis shows that there were significant differences in physical function within the control group participants (H = 382.61, p = 0.001).

Across-Groups Comparison of Physical Function of Participants at baseline, 4th, 8th and 12th week

The mean of physical function of participant in GS group at baseline was 62.53±7.21 and that of CS and control groups were 57.43 ±5.84 and 52.59 ±3.97 respectively. The result of Kruskalwallis shows that there were significant differences in physical function among the participant across the three groups at baseline (H= 25.40, p = 0.001). The mean of physical function of participant in GS group at 4th week was 52.11 ±6.83 while that of CS and control groups are presented in Table 10. The result of Kruskal-wallis shows that there were significant differences in physical function among the participant across the three groups at 4th week (H= 13.15, p= 0.001). Also, the mean of physical function of participant in GS, CS and control groups at 8th and 12th weeks are presented in Table 10. The result of Kruskal-wallis shows that there were significant differences in physical function among the participant across the three groups at 8th week (H= 25.85, p= 0.001) and 12th week (H= 19.89, p= 0.001) respectively

Table 9: Within-Groups Comparison of Physical Functions (N=26)

									H	P
	Mean	±SD	Mean	±SD	Mean	±SD	Mean	±SD		
Glucosamine Sulphate	62.53	7.21	52.11	6.83	44.01	6.65	37.05	5.92	205.63	0.001
Chondroitin Sulphate	57.43	5.84	46.50	6.30	36.76	4.28	29.98	3.22	423.37	0.001
Isometric Quad Ex	52.59	3.97	46.05	4.05	37.82	4.00	31.16	4.56	382.61	0.001

Note: Significant at p < 0.05

Table 10: Across-Groups Comparison of Physical Functions (N=26)

PF	Mean Rank			H	p
	Glucosamine sulphate	Chondroitin sulphate	Control		
Baseline	62.53	57.43	52.59	25.40	0.001
4 th week	2.11	46.72	45.82	13.15	0.001
8 th week	4.01	36.73	37.82	25.85	0.001
12 th week	7.05	29.98	32.75	19.89	0.001

Note: Significant at p < 0.05; PF=Physical function

Discussion

Osteoarthritis of the knee is the most common cause of chronic disability among the elderly worldwide and they mostly experience functional limitations in activities of daily living [42]. The major consequence of knee OA in the lower extremity is functional impairment in Activities of Daily Living with resultant disability; hence, there should be quest to seek for better means of interventions that will be effective. In this current report, the pain intensity experienced by participants in the three groups reduced significantly; and the knee range of motions improved significantly at

the 12th week of interventions. The within group assessment for participants who had glucosamine sulphate iontophoresis further lent credence to the effectiveness of administration of GS in alleviating pain in patient with knee OA as reported by [37, 38, 13]. Glucosamine supplementation had been documented to provide degree of pain relief and improved function in persons who experience regular knee pain, which may be caused by prior cartilage injury and/or OA [16,34].

It is noteworthy that the pain intensity experienced by participants in the CS group was significantly lesser than

that of GS group but quadriceps strengthening exercise showed better efficacy compared to iontophoretic administration of GS and CS. However, there were no significant differences in range of motions across the 3 groups. This current observation corroborated that of Onigbinde et al who also reported that there was no significant difference in the ROMs after 12 weeks and they attributed it to the likelihood of plateau in joint gained motions after 3 months [13]. However, within the groups, there was significant increase in active knee flexion. This is in consistent with the findings of Onigbinde et al. who reported that there was an increase in the ROM of patient with knee OA following the administration of GS for within group assessment [34].

The improved physical functions observed in this study might be attributed to significantly lowered pain experienced by the patient because previous reports by Aghdam et al., Odole and Onigbinde et al. reported that there was significant inverse correlation between pain intensity and WOMAC scores on active knee flexion implying that the lower the former the higher the level of functional activities of the patients [39, 40, 41]. Generally, the trend of pain relief, increased range of motions and improved physical functions in this current study following the three modes of interventions suggested that the drugs are bioavailable to exert effects and that exercise therapy improves general functions. Exercise therapy improves the degree of flexibility of the quadriceps and hamstring group of muscles contributing to smooth and precise ambulatory functions. This corroborated previous report of Braham et al, that glucosamine alleviates pain and subsequently improves the physical functions of patients [16]. Lee et al. strongly suggested that a high and sustainable level of glucosamine in the blood could be achieved via a topical application of topical glucosamine cream and which was able to provide enzymes with a sufficient amount of substrate for the processes of cartilage regeneration and rehabilitation [42]. Several clinical trials have demonstrated the chondroprotective action of glucosamine and chondroitin. Two dual mechanisms had been proposed. Firstly, the basic components of cartilage and synovial fluid, stimulates the anabolic process of the cartilage metabolism; while the second was that anti-inflammatory action can delay many inflammation-induced catabolic processes in the cartilage. These two mechanisms are able to slow the progression of cartilage destruction and may help to regenerate the joint structure, leading to reduced pain and increased mobility of the affected joint.

The administration of glucosamine (GS) and chondroitin sulphate (CS) iontophoresis significantly improved physical function of all the participants in the individual groups at 12th week, although, the

participants who had quadriceps strengthening programmes showed higher physical functions than those who received iontophoresis [43].

Conclusion

In conclusion, quadriceps strengthening exercises showed supremacy than glucosamine and chondroitin sulphate iontophoresis in alleviating pain, increasing active knee flexion range of motion and improving physical functions. There was no supremacy over one another in improving active knee flexion range of motion.

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Appendix

Table 3: Within-Groups Comparison of Pain Intensities and Ranges of Motions of Participants (N=26)

	Variables	Baseline		4th week		8 th week		12th week		f-ratio	p-value
		Mean	SD	Mean	±SD	Mean	SD	Mean	±SD		
Glucosamine*	Pain Intensity	66.54	0.92	48.85	8.64	40.77	.28	30.77	6.88	79.44	0.001
	Range of Motion	96.39	8.86	105.42	7.64	110.89	.87	119.23	5.44	31.82	0.001
Chondroitin*	Pain Intensity	71.54	.75	51.54	10.47	33.85	.83	15.77	9.02	30.08	0.001
	Range of Motion	92.39	0.28	104.54	8.77	115.69	.30	124.42	5.64	20.72	0.001
Quad Exercise	Pain Intensity	66.40	.10	46.92	10.87	31.20	.81	16.80	6.27	41.68	0.001
	Range of Motion	97.76	6.06	107.46	8.98	116.92	.20	120.48	22.82	4.61	0.001

Note: *Sulphate; Significant at p < 0.05

